

A COMPACT THERMOSONIC INSPECTION SYSTEM FOR THE INSPECTION OF COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

A portable thermosonic inspection system has been developed incorporating a miniature microbolometer array camera. The vibrations excited during a test are monitored using a high frequency microphone and assessed automatically to validate the test. The system has been trialled on aerospace components containing impact damage.

Keywords: Thermography, composites, non-destructive evaluation, impact damage

INTRODUCTION

The thermosonic technique (also known as ultrasonically stimulated thermography, vibro-thermography and sonic IR) [1-6] is currently gaining considerable interest worldwide as an alternative means of inspection that has many potential applications. Thermosonic inspection involves the generation of large amplitude vibrations in a test piece to cause frictional heating at crack surfaces that can be imaged by an infrared camera. Typically, these vibrations are produced by an ultrasonic plastic welding horn being pressed against a surface on the part under inspection. Operating frequencies range from 15 to 40 kHz. The technique has the attractions: of being very rapid; of large area coverage and of providing a simple direct image of detected defects. It has been demonstrated to have great potential for the detection of cracks in gas turbine engine parts [7,8] and for the detection of impact damage in composites [9]. These two specific applications differ in one significant way: for the first, the parts are comparatively small and can be brought to an inspection station whereas for the second, the parts are large and it will be necessary for the inspection system to be portable and taken to the parts requiring inspection, the composite wing of an aircraft for example. This paper outlines the design and construction of a compact portable thermosonic inspection system developed for the inspection of composite components.

INSPECTION SYSTEM REQUIREMENTS

A practical inspection system for large composite structures has the following requirements:

- The system should be light in weight and compact to enable the inspector to move it comfortably about the part to be inspected.
- The system should reliably detect all defects above a known sensitivity limit.
- The system output should require a minimum or no expert interpretation.

- The operation of the system should be automatic, performing all necessary reliability checks before exhibiting output images showing the presence or absence of defects.

The thermosonic system that is described below was designed to satisfy all of these requirements.

COMPACT THERMOSONIC SYSTEM DESIGN

Thermosonic inspections involve two pieces of equipment: an ultrasonic excitation horn and an infrared camera. Previously, workers have used conventional cooled semiconductor focal plane array infrared cameras. These are bulky and are many kilograms in weight. We have recently evaluated [10] the performance of a miniature microbolometer array infrared camera and showed that, while it is less sensitive than typical cooled semiconductor focal plane array infrared cameras, it appeared adequate for many NDE applications. This camera, the Flir A10, was used in this work. Its dimensions are 37 x 35 x 48 mm and it has a mass of 0.12 kg. This tiny camera was mounted, as illustrated in figure 1, on a simple frame holding the ultrasonic excitation horn. The whole system was designed to allow the horn to be pressed, with two hands, against the part to be inspected whilst the camera collects thermal images, revealing the presence or absence of defects. A Herfurth 35 kHz ultrasonic horn was used, driven by a power amplifier at 50 watts for periods between 1 and 8 seconds, dependent on achieving required vibration amplitude to image defects.

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of compact thermosonic system.

Experimental studies indicated that reliable thermosonic images of impact damage were obtained when the horn was pressed against composite parts with a force of between 30 and 80 N. This contact force is achieved by pressing the horn against the part surface via a spring. The four contact feet are set to come into contact with the part when the spring is compressed the appropriate distance, eg ~ 10 mm to apply a force of 55 N. A small sheet of PTFE was attached to the horn tip to act as a contact layer between the horn and the part.

ULTRASONIC EXCITATION LEVEL MONITORING

It is now well known that the ultrasonic excitation produced in parts by the application of high power ultrasonic horns takes the form of a complicated set of vibrations that vary in both frequency and amplitude during the period of excitation. In addition, the excitation process is not reproducible; very different spectra of vibrations being generated from one horn-part contact to another. It has been found advantageous [11] to couple a horn to a part via a layer of compliant material, such as duct tape. The result is that the horn is loosely coupled and acts as an ultrasonic hammer that chatters against the part surface. This becomes a complex nonlinear vibration excitation process that produces a large number of harmonics and sub-harmonics and it has been suggested [11,12] that a condition of “acoustic chaos” can be reached that is particularly favourable to crack heating. The non-repeatability is thought to result from the inherent nonlinearity of the excitation process.

The acknowledged non-repeatability of the ultrasonic excitation process introduces the danger of the excitation energy, at a particular horn-part contact, being lower than is necessary to produce sufficient frictional heating at a defect for its detection by thermal imaging. To guard against this possibility it is necessary to make an assessment of vibrational excitation energy achieved in each test. This assessment involves making a measurement of the amplitude and frequency characteristics of the vibrations excited in a part during the excitation process and computing a parameter that estimates the heating potential of these vibrations at a defect. This parameter has been called the “heating index”.

The heating index.

Previous [13] thermosonic studies of fatigue cracks in steel beams established a relationship between the frictional heating observed at a crack and the acoustic damping caused by the crack to mechanical vibrations excited in a beam. In this work, the beams were excited by a ~0.6 second burst of ultrasonic horn excitation. The vibrations in the beams were monitored by strain gauges and the resulting vibration spectra were analysed throughout the ~0.6 second burst of excitation. The vibration spectra were found to be rich in harmonics that varied in amplitude throughout the period of the excitation pulse. In addition, these characteristics were found to lack reproducibility, in agreement with the findings of others, mentioned above. A relationship was demonstrated between the frictional heating energy at a crack and the damping of beam vibrations caused by the presence of the crack. This necessitated the quantification of the damping of all the vibrational modes recorded during the excitation pulses.

The assumption was made that the temperature rise produced at a crack is related directly to the power (P) dissipated at the crack during vibration. The power dissipated at the crack is given by [14]:

$$P = 2\pi\eta_{crack}fV \quad (1)$$

where η_{crack} is the crack loss factor, f is the mode vibration frequency and V is the mode strain energy. Since V is proportional to vibration amplitude A squared,

$$P \propto fA^2 \quad (2)$$

This parameter has been termed [15] “the energy index”, EI, of a vibration. In thermosonic tests numerous vibrational modes are excited and EI may be computed using:

$$EI = \sum_n W_n A_n^2 \quad (3)$$

In which the sum is taken over the n excited modes and the weight $W_n = f_n/f_0$ is the “weight” of the n^{th} frequency component and is computed as the ratio of the frequency, f_n , to a reference frequency which was chosen as the centre frequency of the exciter, f_0 (=35 kHz in our case). As the amplitudes of the excited modes are found to vary throughout the duration of an excitation pulse, the value of EI given by equation (3) must be regarded as an instantaneous value. The heating observed at an instant of time, τ , at the surface around a crack will be the sum of the heating generated at the surface by the crack and the heating generated at earlier times by the crack below the surface that has diffused to the surface to contribute to the total heating at time τ . It has been suggested [15] that a measure of the total heating, termed the “heating index”, HI, can be obtained from the energy index by:

$$HI(\tau) = \int_0^{\tau} e^{k(t-\tau)} EI(t) dt \quad (4)$$

where t is the time integration variable and k is a decay constant which can be estimated from the temporal decay of heating when the excitation is switched off. It was found experimentally that there was a good correlation between the heating index and the temperature rise at a crack, observed using thermography. It was also shown that a certain threshold value of HI needed to be exceeded for an image of a crack to be obtained, ie for the temperature rise to exceed the noise level of the infrared camera employed.

The strategy that has been developed to ensure the reliability of thermosonic inspection, is to monitor the energy index during the excitation phase of a test and from this to compute the heating index to check that it exceeds the threshold found necessary to form images of the types of defect sought. The determination of the threshold heating index is an experimental process necessitating data from repeat tests of samples containing a representative range of defects of the type sought, eg parts with cracks having a range of sizes.

In the laboratory work the excited vibrations were monitored using strain gauges bonded to the parts under test. This is not suitable for the in-field inspection of composite parts. It has been found [16] that the same vibrations can be effectively monitored using a high frequency microphone. This microphone, a B&K 4138-A-015 mounted on a B&K 2670 preamplifier is incorporated into the compact thermosonic inspection system, on the camera mounting post, fig. 1. During the excitation phase of a

test, data from the microphone is collected using a high frequency sampling oscilloscope (Picoscope 5230). Short-time Fourier transformation algorithms are used to compute the vibration spectra throughout the excitation phase and from these the heating indices are obtained in the way indicated above. The determination of the thermal decay function and the heating index threshold for composite parts will be explained below.

IMAGE PROCESSING

The purposes of the image processing programme that is an integral part of this thermosonic inspection system are:

- to obtain adequate imaging sensitivity from the low specification miniature microbolometer array camera.
- to collect and combine all thermosonic signals produced in an inspection.
- to provide a simple validated output that requires no expert interpretation.

The noise level in images obtained from the uncooled Flir A10 microbolometer array camera is ~80 mK whilst for cooled semiconductor focal plane array cameras that are usually used for NDE its is ~20 mK. In addition the A10 array is 160 x120 pixels while 320 x 256, or higher, is typical of cooled cameras. The great advantage of the A10 for this application is its small size and light weight but its low specification necessitates a range of image processing steps to obtain reliable images of adequate sensitivity. These steps are detailed below.

Background subtraction

Prior to each test, the part under inspection is imaged for 2 seconds (50 frames collected) to establish the “background” IR image of the part. The 50 frames are averaged to produce a reliable estimation of the signal in each pixel of the image. This background image is then subtracted from each image collected during the ultrasonic excitation of the part. The resulting images are of the thermosonic heating alone, separated from effects caused by variations in surface emissivity across the part or the reflection of external IR sources (such as the inspector). Figure 2a is a raw thermosonic image of an area of a composite part that has been impact damaged. Figure 2b shows the result of background subtraction from the raw data. It is evident that a thermal gradient across test piece, fig 2a, diagonally lower left to upper right, has been removed by the background subtraction.

Figure 2. a) Raw IR thermosonic image. b) image after background subtraction.

Low pass filtering

Although evidence of the impact damage can be seen in figure 2b, it is a weak image, little above the intrinsic temporal noise level of the microbolometer array camera. This noise can be reduced by low pass filtering. The expected true thermal behaviour for composites is a monotonic increase in temperature during excitation and decrease after it. A low pass filter can be used to extract the high frequency noise that is a characteristic of the microbolometer array. The effect of 5 Hz low pass filtering on the data forming the image, fig. 2b, is shown in figure 3 a. The impact damage is revealed as a region of heating just below the centre of the image. The cold bar across the upper part of the image is an edge of the test piece.

Clipping

An objective of the image processing programme is to remove subjective judgement and to only present images that have some quantitative certainty of being the result of heating caused by the ultrasonic excitation. The criterion that has been adopted here is to set to zero all pixel signals that are below three standard deviations of the noise level, determined by the analysis of the pre-excitation background image data. This process retains only those elements of an image collected during excitation that can be reliably attributed to the thermosonic heating process.

Integration

The ultrasonic excitation pulse may have a duration of between ~0.5 and ~8 seconds, depending on the thermal characteristics of the test material. Whilst individual images collected during excitation may show evidence of defects, a far stronger and clearer image is formed by integrating all the images collected during the excitation pulse. Figure 3b shows the image of the defect obtained after clipping and integrating all the images collected during the excitation pulse.

Salt and pepper noise filtering

Figure 3b is a strong image of the defect but it is surrounded by a distracting field of individual pixel signals, called "salt and pepper noise". This can be removed by salt and pepper noise filter, resulting in the image in figure 3c.

Binarization

The final process is to binarize the image, setting all pixel signals above zero to the same level, resulting in the image shown in figure 3d. This is the final image presented to the inspector. It shows in the simplest possible way the areas of the part, within the field of view, that emitted excess infrared radiation during the ultrasonic excitation. The number of pixels indicating a defect is also presented as an indication of defect area.

Figure 3. a) Best contrast image after background subtraction and low-pass filter. b) integrated image. c) image after salt and pepper filter application. d) final binarized image and estimation of number of damage pixels.

DETERMINATION OF HEATING INDEX FOR COMPOSITE PARTS

The heating index, explained above, was developed in studies of cracks in metallic parts. For these, the ultrasonic excitation horn was typically driven using a 1kW power amplifier output for 0.6 seconds. For composite parts, however, it is undesirable to apply excitation horns operating at such high power levels because it is known that these can cause resin melting damage. It has been found [9] that composites can be inspected using far lower power levels (~10 to 50 watts) if longer periods of excitation are used (~2 to 8 seconds). The reason for this is the very much lower thermal conductivity of composite materials compared with metals. A further consequence of this low conductivity is a far slower decay in local heating produced at a defect by ultrasonic excitation. Whilst it proved possible to approximate the decay after thermosonic heating by a simple single exponential decay process for metallic parts, this has not been found to be the case for the slower decay found in composites. As this decay process needs to be incorporated into the heating index calculation, equation 4, it is necessary to characterize it experimentally. This has been done by studying the decay

of heating observed at a typical impact damage defect, following ultrasonic excitation, and evaluating a set of exponential fitting curves able to represent the cooling for a period equal to the excitation time.

Figure 4a is the time history of the vibration signal acquired by the microphone during the excitation of a composite part. The peaks in amplitude at the beginning and end of the excitation process are commonly observed in composites. Figure 4b represents the signal time-frequency decomposition which is used to calculate energy index (equation 3). It shows a rich pattern of harmonics and sub-harmonics varying in amplitude throughout the excitation (horn excitation frequency was 35 kHz). Figure 4c shows the heating index (equation 4) computed from the energy index, as explained above. The peak value of this heating index, 3000, is used as a measure of the strength of the ultrasonic excitation achieved in the part that can be compared with the experimentally established threshold value to assess the adequacy of the excitation for a reliable test.

Figure 4. a) Microphone signal during excitation. b) Short Time Fourier Transform of microphone signal. c) Heating index of excitation pulse.

THE COMPACT PORTABLE THERMOSONIC INSPECTION SYSTEM

The hand held system is connected by three umbilical cables to the power supplies for the horn and camera and to the conditioning unit for the microphone. All the data collection and data processing requirements are met by a dual processor laptop computer.

A block diagram of the system operating procedure is shown in figure 5. This procedure is activated by a button on the hand-held system when the operator has applied sufficient force to bring the four feet into contact with the test piece. The first operation is to obtain the background image. After this, the horn is activated for a pre-set period of time (between 2 and 8 seconds), previously determined to be required for the part under test. During this time, images from the IR camera and signals from the microphone are stored in the computer. At the end of the excitation period an audible signal is emitted by the laptop to indicate to the operator that the test is complete and that the hand-held system can be removed from contact with the test piece. Once the heating index obtained in the test has been computed it is displayed on the laptop. The operator is then required to decide if it is adequate, based on previous experience with parts of the type under inspection containing defects of the type sought. If the heating index is adequate, the full image processing procedure is applied to the stored images and a final image is displayed on the laptop. If the heating index is inadequate, the test is abandoned and repeated. The area covered in each test is 30x25 cm².

Figure.5. Flow chart of thermosonic standard operation procedure

CONCLUSIONS

A prototype compact thermosonic inspection system has been developed for the inspection of large composite parts or structures. The system meets the design requirements of :

- being compact and light in weight
- having an automated operating system
- providing a rapid inspection
- performing reliability checks on adequacy of excitation levels
- providing a simple visual output requiring a minimum of expert interpretation

The system produced is a demonstrator system, making use of commercially available parts and the control programmes are written in the development language MatLab. There remains scope for considerable further reductions in the size and weight of the hand-held unit and the control electronics through custom design and fabrication of components. Similarly, there is scope for improving the software, in particular the removal of the need for operator intervention in assessing heating index adequacy. However, the system that has been presented here has successfully demonstrated the ways that thermosonics can be packaged to provide a practical, reliable and rapid means of inspection for composite parts or structures.

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